

Healthy Ramadan Campaign 2025: A Community-Led Approach to Fasting and Wellbeing

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Background:

The Healthy Ramadan Campaign 2025 was a nationwide initiative designed to support Muslim communities in maintaining their wellbeing during the holy month. Recognising the importance of accessible, culturally appropriate health education, the campaign provided evidence-based guidance on nutrition, hydration, and medication management. A key aim was to empower local communities to lead structured educational sessions, ensuring practical advice reached a broad and diverse audience.

Methods:

Over 100 mosques and community centres across the UK registered to host health education sessions. Facilitators were provided with toolkits containing ready-made presentations, feedback forms, and promotional materials. Approximately 35 interactive sessions were delivered, focusing on safe fasting, healthy eating, and the management of long-term conditions. Feedback was collected using standardised forms to assess levels of engagement, knowledge gained, and areas for improvement.

Results:

The campaign was well received, with more than 1,200 participants attending sessions and 85% rating the content as clear, relevant, and easy to apply. Attendees appreciated the culturally sensitive approach and practical advice tailored to the realities of fasting.

Suggestions for improvement included incorporating more group discussions, example meal plans, and clearer guidance on medication use, particularly for those living with diabetes and other chronic conditions. Stakeholders also recommended the introduction of daily digital health reminders to further extend the campaign's reach and impact.

Challenges and Lessons Learnt:

While the campaign successfully delivered its core educational objectives, feedback highlighted the need for more personalised dietary and medical advice. The inclusion of healthcare professionals in future sessions was suggested to address this gap. Furthermore, the need for a more systematic approach to tracking engagement and outcomes was identified, to better evaluate the campaign's effectiveness.

Conclusion:

The Healthy Ramadan Campaign 2025 demonstrated the value of a structured, community-driven approach to health promotion during Ramadan. Looking ahead, the campaign will integrate expert-led sessions, digital health messaging, and more interactive content to enhance personalisation and engagement. These developments will support fasting individuals in managing their health more confidently, contributing to improved long-term wellbeing within Muslim communities.